

MASTER DISSERTATION

**Research FDI Economic Effects on Domestic
Investment in Cape Verde**

Research FDI economic Effects on Domestic Investment in Cape Verde

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ABSTRACT

Promoting economic growth is a central element of any governments policy. For some countries, especially less developed ones, attracting foreign direct investment (FDI) has been a critical factor in achieving economic growth. Numerous studies have investigated the impact of FDI inflows on the host country's economy; however, the findings remain heterogeneous. FDI may have positive, negative, or even neutral effects on the host country's economy (Johnson, 2005; Geijer, 2009; Rahman, 2015). Recent studies have further pointed out that the impact of FDI strongly depends on the host country absorptive capacity (Adams, 2009). In fact, the results also depend on how FDI affects domestic investment (DI), that is, crowding-in or crowding-out effects. Accordingly, evidence of crowding-out is a strong reason to question the overall relevance of FDI for economic development.

This thesis aims to research the economic effects of FDI on DI in the Cape Verdean economy for the period of 1986-2015. Considering the country-specific characteristic and its insular nature, it is interesting to examine how FDI affects DI in the Cape Verde islands. To achieve the main objective, the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model and the bounds test for cointegration have been applied in this study.

The results indicate no cointegration among the variables when GDP growth is assumed as the dependent variable. However, when DI is taken as the dependent variable, we find a mixed results. In the short term, the lagged value of FDI has a negative impact on DI, indicating a crowd-out effect. However, this effect decreases over time, leading to a crowd-in effect of FDI on domestic investment in the long run. Moreover, the results indicate a negative correlation between DI and GDP growth in the long run, contrasting with a positive effect in the short term. DI and GDP growth play a role in driving FDI inflows to the host country; however, the effect is not substantial, suggesting that small market size is not a strong determinant of FDI inflows. Additionally, the coefficient of GDP growth seems the be significantly only in the long run. these findings provide insights for policymakers aiming to balance domestic and foreign investment strategies in small island economies.

Key Words: FDI, Domestic Investment, Crowd in and Crowd out, Economic Growth, Cape Verde.

List of abbreviations

Abbreviations	Details
ADB	African development bank
ADEI	agency for the development of enterprises and innovation
ADF	Augmented Dickey-fuller
AIC	Akaike Information Criterion
ARDL	Autoregressive distributed Lags
DI	Domestic Investment
EBI	European bank of investments
ECOWAS	economic community of West African States
ECT	Error Correlations Terms
EJV	equity joint venture
EU	European Union
FDI	Foreign Direct Investment
GDP	Gross domestic Productions
GFCF	gross fixed capital formation
GMM	generalized method of moments
HIC	Quinn information criterion
IMF	international monetary fund
INE	National Institute of Statistics
MCC	millennium challenge corporation
MNC	Multinational Companies
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation

	and Development
PP	Phillips-Perron
R&D	Research and Development
SIC	Schwarz information criterion
SMEs	small- and medium-sized enterprises
TNCs	transnational companies
UNCTAD	United Nations Conference on Trade and Development
(UN)	united nations
WB	world bank
WEF	World Economic Forum
WFFE	wholly foreign-funded enterprise
WTO	world trade organizations

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CHAPTER 0 INTRODUCTION

0.1 Background

Promoting economic growth is a central element of any governments policy. For some countries, especially less developed ones, attracting foreign direct investment (FDI) has been a critical factor in achieving economic growth. The widespread belief is that FDI can bring more advanced technology and know-how to the host country, which may not be attainable through domestic capital alone. FDI can also stimulate competition, create jobs, enhance management skills, and contribute to overall economic development (Agosin, & Mayer, 2000).

Recently, many studies have investigated the impact of FDI inflows on host country economies. However, the findings remain heterogeneous. Some studies suggest that FDI has a positive effect on economic growth (see: Johnson, 2005; Duarte et al. 2017), while others highlight its negative impact (see: Rahman, 2015). Still, others report neutral effects (Herzer et al 2008; Geijer, 2009). Furthermore, research shows that the impact of FDI is conditional on a country's absorptive capacity, including its human capital, financial development, technology, and infrastructure, (See: Adams, (2009); Luiz de Mello (1997); Frimpong, & Oteng-Abayie, 2006). The effects of FDI also depend on the capabilities of domestic firms (Chudnovsky, & López, 2008), and on whether FDI crowds in or crowds out domestic investment (Tülüce, & Doğan, (2014). In other words, FDI may stimulate new downstream or upstream investments that would not otherwise occur, or it may displace domestic investment opportunities. If FDI fails to contribute to capital formation in the host country, this raises important questions about the benefits of FDI inflows (Agosin & Mayer, 2000).

Therefore, it is important to examine how FDI affects domestic investment in the Cape Verde islands. However, this topic has not been sufficiently researched in the context of insular economies, specifically Cape Verde. This thesis seeks to fill this gap in the literature. The main objective is to evaluate the economic effects of FDI on domestic investment in Cape Verde over the period 1986–2015. By conducting this research, we aim to improve understanding of the relationship between FDI and domestic investment in the Cape Verdean economy, providing insights for

policymakers seeking to balance domestic and foreign direct investment strategies in small island economies.

0.2 Source of the Topic

Cape Verde's insular nature, its unique economic characteristics, and recent policy initiatives to attract foreign capital provide the motivation for this study. The chosen topic: The economic effects of FDI on domestic investment in Cape Verde, seeks to enhance understanding of the relationship between FDI and domestic investment, while offering insights for policymakers in shaping effective investment strategies.

0.3 Objectives and Importance of the Research

This thesis aims to evaluate the impact of FDI on domestic investment in Cape Verde over the period 1986–2015. Given the country's insular nature and unique economic characteristics, the study provides valuable insights not only for policymakers in Cape Verde but also for other small island economies facing similar challenges. Specifically, the research addresses the following questions:

1. Does FDI crowd in or crowd out domestic investment in Cape Verde?
2. To what extent do domestic investment and GDP growth influence FDI inflows into the country?

0.4 Research Method

This study employs an econometric approach to achieve its research objectives. Specifically, the autoregressive distributed lags (ARDL) model and the bounds test for co-integration are applied to examine long-run economic relationships among variables. This methodology has been widely adopted in previous studies with similar research aims. All estimations are carried out using EViews 10.

0.5 Innovations

This study contributes to the literature by examining FDI and domestic investment in the context of a small insular economy, Cape Verde. Previous research has largely focused on large developing or developed economies, which, while insightful, cannot

be directly generalized to small island states. The existing literature remains heterogeneous and/or inconclusive regarding the impact of FDI on domestic investment and economic growth. By addressing this gap, the study provides new evidence on how FDI influences domestic investment in a small island economy.

0.6 Thesis structure

Chapter 0 – This chapter introduces the topic and provides background on the effects of FDI on economic growth and domestic investment. It also presents the objectives, significance of the research, methodology, and source of the topic

Chapter 1- This chapter presents the literature review. It provides a detailed discussion of previous studies on the effects of FDI in host countries and its impact on domestic investment, highlighting how domestic investment benefits from FDI.

Chapter 2- This chapter discusses FDI and economic development in Cape Verde. Specifically, it evaluates FDI inflows into the country and the country's economic growth over recent years.

Chapter 3- This chapter outlines the methodology applied to achieve the study's objectives and provides details on the data used in the analysis.

Chapter 4- This chapter presents the main empirical findings and conducts stability tests for the model.

Chapter 5- This chapter provides the study's main conclusions, policy implications, limitations, and suggestions for future research.

CHAPTER 1 THE LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1 The Effects of FDI on Economic Growth in the Host Country

Recently, FDI has increased significantly in most developing countries, emerging economies, and countries in transition. This rapid growth of FDI has been accompanied by policymakers in developing countries placing greater emphasis on attracting foreign capital. Many countries have reduced barriers to FDI, offering tax incentives and subsidies, with the strong belief that FDI can promote economic growth (Herzer, Klasen, & Felicitas, 2008).

FDI is widely believed to provide significant benefits to host countries, including technology spillovers, human capital formation, enhanced competitiveness, and enterprise development (Kurtishi-Kastrati, 2013). Empirical studies (De Mello, 1997; Johnson, 2006; Göçer, Mercan, & Peker, 2014; Rahman, 2015; Chowdhury, & Mavrotas, 2005) reinforce the latter findings.

According to exogenous growth theory, FDI contributes to capital accumulation by introducing new stock of goods and foreign technology, affecting economic growth primarily in the short run. Alternatively, endogenous growth theory emphasizes that FDI can stimulate long-term growth through knowledge accumulation, technology transfer, and human capital development. Technological progress and labor augmentation further support sustained growth over time (Elboiashi, 2011), (Barro and Sala-I-Martin 1995).

Some studies argue that the impact of FDI on growth is similar to that of domestic investment (Herzer et al. 2008); however, endogenous growth theory generally suggests that FDI is more productive than domestic investment. FDI also facilitates the absorption of new technologies into the host country's production functions (Borensztein, Gregorio, & Lee, 1998). In line with above, (De Mello 1999) emphasize that, in the long run, economic growth is supported through enhanced knowledge, labor training, skill acquisition, and the introduction of alternative management practices and organizational arrangements.

Overall, FDI promotes economic growth through both capital accumulation and knowledge spillovers, (Herzer et al. 2008).

Theoretically, FDI is often considered more important for economic growth than domestic investment or other capital flows. The main rationale is that FDI provides a comprehensive bundle of resources, including physical capital, modern technology and production techniques, managerial expertise, and market knowledge. These advantages tend to spill over to domestic enterprises in the host country, thereby resulting in higher levels of efficiency and productivity (Colen et al 2008). Consequently, FDI can contribute more effectively to accelerating economic growth in host countries (Elboiashi, 2011). However, some researchers argue that the hypothesis that foreign firms are more efficient than domestic firms is controversial in the literature. (Muteny 2008), for example, investigated the impact of FDI on growth in 32 Sub-Saharan African countries using cross-sectional and dynamic panel data for the period 1990–2003. The results emphasized that while FDI has a positive effect on economic growth, it is less efficient than domestic investment.

Although it is generally accepted that FDI positively affects economic growth, empirical literature has not reached a clear consensus on the magnitude or nature of its impact (Campos and Kinoshita 2002). One reason for this uncertainty is that theory often equates FDI with technological transfer, while in reality FDI encompasses a wide range of arrangements that extend far beyond technology transfer. The supposed benefits of FDI for host economies are also questioned, as empirical studies have failed to consistently establish a significant positive impact, for example (Adams, 2009 from SSA Countries; Geijer, 2009 from México; Rahman, Naguib, 2010 from Argentine; Rahman, 2015 from Bangladesh).

Other studies highlight that the effects of FDI on economic growth depend on country-specific conditions, such as income level, human capital development, openness to trade, financial development, infrastructure, and institutional quality (Blomstrom et al. 1992; Borensztein et al. 1998; Makki and Somwaru 2004; Chowdhury and Mavrotas 2006; Colen et al. 2008; Rui & Forte 2010; Kurtishi-Kastrati, 2013). Following Alfaro et al 2004, the impact of FDI on economic growth tends to be more favorable in countries with advanced financial markets. Similarly, FDI appears to positively affect growth when directed toward the manufacturing

sector, negatively in the primary sector, and with mixed results in the service sector (Elboiashi, 2011).

(Blomstrom et al. 1992), analysing 78 developing countries, found that FDI is more beneficial for high-income developing countries than for low-income ones. This suggests that host countries must reach a certain threshold of development before fully benefiting from FDI. Similarly, (Razin 2003) argues that the effects of FDI on economic growth depend not only on the volume of foreign capital but also on the level of domestic development.

(Adams, & Opoku, 2015) examined the effects of FDI and regulations on the economic growth of 22 SSA countries during the period 1980–2011 using GMM estimation. The results show that neither FDI nor regulatory variables had an independent positive effect on economic growth. Instead, the impact of FDI in SSA economies was strongly conditioned by host-country policies.

1.2 The Role of FDI at the Micro Level

Empirical studies examining the effects of FDI on host countries can generally be classified into two main types: those that focus on the role of FDI at the macro/aggregate level, particularly its impact on economic growth, and those that analyze microeconomic data at the industry/sector or firm level (Elboiashi, Hosein, 2011). Building on the hypothesis that multinational corporations (MNCs) are more advanced than domestic firms—especially in developing economies due to their superior technology, economies of scale, and enhanced management practices (Lall 1978), several studies have tested whether foreign firms are indeed technologically more advanced than domestic ones (Colen et al. 2008).

For example, (Eregha 2012) applied the generalized method of moments (GMM) and two-stage least squares estimation techniques, finding that domestic firms often lack the technical know-how and absorptive capacity required to benefit from the technological spillovers of FDI inflows. Moreover, underdeveloped infrastructure and inefficient financial systems hinder their ability to compete with foreign counterparts. Similarly, (Alsadiq 2013) found a robust negative relationship between outward FDI

and the rate of domestic investment, which can be explained by capital scarcity and imperfect financial markets.

Other studies reinforce these findings. (Konara & Wei 2017), show that foreign firms are generally larger, more productive, more active, and more profitable than domestic firms. However, they also report that FDI can have negative spillover effects on domestic productivity. (Rossi 2008), likewise found that transnational company (TNC) affiliates demonstrated higher productivity compared to domestic firms. On the other hand, domestic firms with strong absorptive capacity are more likely to benefit positively from the presence of TNCs, while those with weak absorptive capacity may experience limited or even negative spillovers.

The productivity benefits for domestic firms appear to be only partially correlated with the presence of foreign projects. (Javorcik 2004) argues that spillover effects are not necessarily linked to the presence of MNCs within the same industry. Similarly, (Fan 2016) suggests that it is difficult for domestic firms to capture the potential spillover benefits of MNCs when a substantial technology gap exists between them. (Kosová 2010) further shows that the primary beneficiaries of technology spillovers are often firms operating in technologically advanced industries.

However, the presence of foreign firms can also create competitive pressures. As (Kokko & Thang, 2014) note, foreign entrants may capture market share, forcing local firms to reduce output, cut prices, or, in the case of less efficient firms, exit the industry altogether.

(Aitken, & Harrison, 1999), using a panel of more than 4,000 Venezuelan factory between 1976 and 1989, found two key effects of FDI on domestic firms' productivity. First, increases in foreign equity participation were positively associated with productivity gains in recipient factories with fewer than 50 employees, suggesting that such factories benefited from the productive advantages of foreign ownership. Second, they observed that the productivity of entirely domestic firms in the same industry was negatively affected by rising levels of foreign ownership.

1.3 The Spillovers Effects

Foreign firms have been considered one of the best channels through which technology transfer occurs. Likewise, spillover effects produced by MNC can take different forms and channels through which they take place. One of the best reasons for attracting MNC and associated with FDI for the host country is to improve domestic firm's productivity. Strongly correlated with the concept of productivity or technology, wherein it personalizes the fact that foreign enterprises own intangible assets, once they can be passed to domestic firms and consequently enhance their productivity level. (Elboiashi, 2011).

Blomstrom and Kokko (1999), point out two main reasons why MNC affiliates may differ from domestic firms in host countries. First, MNCs bring proprietary technology, which constitutes their firm-specific advantage, enabling them to compete successfully. They also tend to have greater knowledge of local markets, consumer preferences, and business practices. Second, the entry of MNCs disrupts market equilibrium, compelling domestic firms to take actions to protect their market shares and profits. These dynamics may generate different types of spillovers.

The first type is productivity spillovers, which occur when the presence of MNCs leads to an increase in the productivity of domestic firms, and the MNCs cannot fully internalize the value of these benefits, (Javorcik 2004). Such spillovers often arise from the competitive pressures introduced by MNCs, which push domestic firms to use existing technologies and resources more efficiently, (Elboiashi, 2011). In some cases, heightened competition forces domestic firms to adopt new and more efficient technologies (Blomstrom and Kokko 1998; Javorcik, (2004). Another type is market spillovers, which occur when the entry of MNCs enables domestic firms to gain better access to export markets (Colen et al. 2008).

MNCs typically possess stronger managerial and organizational capabilities, as well as superior marketing and distribution systems, compared to domestic firms—especially in developing economies (Elboiashi, 2011). However, high fixed costs associated with infrastructure, transport, communication, and financial services are essential for facilitating export activities (Blomstrom and Kokko 1990). MNCs may also engage in horizontal FDI, producing in the host country the same types of goods

they produce at home (Caves 1971). This can generate horizontal spillovers at the industry level, though sometimes domestic firms are unable to keep pace with the superior performance of foreign competitors, which may force them to reduce market shares (Stancik 2007).

A further category is vertical spillovers, which arise when MNCs engage in vertical FDI by producing goods or inputs in the host country that feed into their production processes (Caves 1971). Domestic firms in different sectors may be affected if they directly supply or purchase from foreign affiliates (Stancik 2007). However, vertical spillovers are often found to generate fewer benefits for domestic firms compared to horizontal spillovers, especially when MNCs primarily exploit cheap labor and export their goods rather than integrating with local markets (Søreide, 2001); (Filippo Reganati, & Edgardo Sica. 2007).

Several studies identify the main channels of spillover effects from FDI to domestic firms: imitation, human capital formation, competition, crowding-in and crowding-out, and export linkages (Gorg and Greenaway 2003) (Javorcik, 2004) and (Blomstrom and Kokko 1998). Imitation occurs when domestic firms copy products, technologies, or production processes. While advanced technologies may require high technical skills, managerial and organizational practices are often easier to imitate (Colen et al. 2008). Human capital spillovers occur when MNCs contribute to skill development through training, education, or R&D investment. Training can be formal or informal, ranging from on-the-job learning to specialized education centers established by MNCs (Colen et al. 2008). These effects can be both horizontal (via labor turnover, where trained workers move to domestic firms) and vertical (when suppliers or buyers directly benefit from training). While labor turnover spillovers may take time to materialize, supplier training can generate immediate productivity gains (Elboiashi, 2011). Competition effects arise when the presence of MNCs intensifies competition in the host economy. Domestic firms may be forced to upgrade technology, improve efficiency, or invest in human capital, even when direct imitation of MNC technologies is not possible (Colen et al. 2008). At the same time, intense competition may also lead to crowding out, where domestic firms lose market share, reduce output, or exit the market due to MNC advantages (Colen et al. 2008); (Elboiashi, 2011). Conversely, crowding in may occur when MNCs create new market opportunities, attract domestic firms into dynamic sectors, and stimulate domestic investment

Borensztein et al., 1998). In weaker institutional settings, however, crowding in may be limited if governments lack the capacity to channel FDI into sectors that complement domestic firms (Agostin and Mayer 2000; Colen et al. 2008). Finally, export spillovers may arise when domestic firms benefit from the export activities of MNCs, which can enhance their international competitiveness (Aitken et al., 1997). The extent of such benefits depends heavily on domestic absorptive capacity—factors such as human capital, financial market development, and the technology gap (Nguyen 2008).

1.4 The Empirical Evidence of the Impact of FDI on Domestic Investment: Crowding-In and Crowding-Out Effects

The empirical evidence on the impact of FDI on domestic investment (DI) is mixed. Some researchers argue that FDI inflows stimulate DI, generating a crowding-in effect. Others suggest that FDI reduces DI by creating competitive pressures, leading to a crowding-out effect (Colen et al. 2008). Moreover, FDI may affect DI indirectly by promoting economic growth, Fry (1993).

De Mello (1999); Agosin & Mayer, 2000), argue that if FDI positively influences economic growth in the host country, it is likely to complement DI, thus crowding it in. However, if FDI and DI act as perfect substitutes, FDI may displace DI, leaving total output unchanged. When they are complementary, both total investment and output increase. Consequently, FDI can stimulate competition in host countries and encourage DI through spillover effects, creating new investment opportunities that might not exist otherwise. On the other hand, FDI also carries the risk of crowding out DI due to the loss of competitiveness, rising costs of capital, or adverse knowledge spillovers (Acar Eriş, & Tekçe, 2012).

Following Alsadiq, (2013), the impact of outward FDI on DI differs across countries, depending both on the motives of multinational corporations (MNCs) and the structural characteristics of the host economy. Two key mechanisms are at play. First, outward FDI may drain domestic financial markets, as MNCs transfer part of their capital abroad, reducing the funds available for DI in financially constrained economies. Second, outward FDI may affect product markets when firms shift

production abroad, with the net impact depending on the underlying motives for investing abroad (Dunning, 1985). Empirical evidence confirms these complexities. Alsadiq, (2013), analyzing 121 developing and transition economies (1990–2010), found a strong negative relationship between outward FDI and DI, with a 1% increase in outward FDI reducing DI by about 29%. This was largely attributed to capital scarcity and imperfect financial markets.

(Agostin and Mayer 2005) using panel data (1970–1996) for Africa, Asia, and Latin America, observed strong crowding-in effects in Asia, weaker effects in Africa, and significant crowding-out in Latin America. The crowding-in effect in Asia was linked to high investment rates and positive linkages between MNCs and local firms, while weak investment and technological capacity explained the contrasting results in Africa and Latin America.

Other studies show similar regional variations. Apergis et al. 2006, using data from 30 countries (1992–2002), found complementary long-run relationships between FDI and DI, with crowding-in effects in Asia and Africa, but crowding-out in Europe and the Americas. (Tang et al. (2006) reported no evidence of crowding-out in China; instead, FDI complemented DI and stimulated growth. Likewise, Gungor, & Ringim, (2017) confirmed significant long-run relationships between FDI, DI, and growth in Nigeria. Some studies highlight differences in the effects of FDI entry modes. Chen, Yao, & Malizard, (2016) showed that in China, equity joint ventures (EJVs) crowd in DI, while wholly foreign-owned enterprises (WFOEs) crowd it out. Ivanović, (2015), reported negative effects of FDI on DI in Croatia, whereas Lean, & Tan, (2011) found complementary effects in Malaysia (1970–2009). Ndikumana, & Verick, (2008), also found that FDI crowds in DI in Sub-Saharan Africa, particularly in countries that improve their investment climate.

Evidence from developed economies is equally diverse. (Faeth 2006) found that in Australia, FDI increased DI and GDP growth but reduced export growth. In Belgium (Backer & Sleuwaegen 2003) observed crowding-out effects on domestic entrepreneurs. (Szkorupová, 2015) found crowding-out effects in Eastern Europe (Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, and Slovakia). (Pilbeam, & Oboleviciute, 2012) analyzing 26 EU countries (1990–2008), showed that FDI crowds in DI in new member states but crowds out DI in older EU-14 countries. See also:

Sector-specific studies also add nuance. (Ahmed et al. 2015) analyzing Uganda (1992–2012), reported neutral effects at the aggregate level, crowding-out in four sectors, crowding-in in two sectors, and mixed effects in three. (Polat 2017), studying 30 OECD countries (2006–2013), found no significant aggregate effect of FDI on DI, though intra-company loans had positive effects on domestic capital formation. (Calderón et al. 2004) reported that both Greenfield and M&A FDI tend to precede DI. (Mišun & Tomšik 2002) found crowding-out effects in Poland, but crowding-in effects in Hungary and the Czech Republic. For further studies we suggest Acar, (Eriş, & Tekçe, 2012).

Overall, the literature shows that the impact of FDI on DI is highly context-dependent, varying across countries, regions, sectors, and methodologies. While some evidence supports positive crowding-in effects, other findings highlight significant crowding-out risks. This suggests that the relationship between FDI and DI remains a subject of debate, shaped by both host-country characteristics and the nature of foreign investment.

1.5 Firm's Capability Factors

The effects of FDI on domestic investment and economic growth in host countries are generally mixed and inconclusive. However, some researchers suggest that certain factors may condition the FDI-led growth hypothesis, particularly in developing economies. For instance, (Nguyen et al. 2009), argue that developing countries benefit from FDI only if they have sufficient absorptive capacity, such as human capital resources, domestic firm capabilities, financial systems, physical infrastructure, technological development, and institutional frameworks. Accordingly, specific policies that enhance host-country absorptive capacity are recommended. Similarly, other researchers argue that the question is not whether FDI influences host countries, but whether the necessary conditions for spillover effects—namely absorptive capacity—are present (Khordagui, & Saleh, 2013). Several studies suggest that the absorptive capacity of the host country can be divided into two main dimensions: Micro-level: absorptive capacity of domestic firms, such as technology gap and qualified labor (Cohen and Levithal, 1990; Girma, 2005; Nguyen, et al. (2009). Macro-level: national absorptive capacity, including technological level, human

capital, financial systems, and institutional development (Keller, 1996; Borensztein, De Gregorio, & 1998); Hermes, & Lensink, 2003; Fu, 2008). When domestic firms interact with foreign firms, if there is at least an initial development in technology, worker skills, and managerial capacity, they are more likely to absorb advanced technologies and business practices from foreign companies. On the other hand, international enterprises may also acquire and integrate domestic firms (Nguyen, et al. 2009).

(Behera, 2015), highlights the importance of absorptive capacity in enabling domestic firms to benefit from foreign firms. By examining whether externalities associated with FDI benefit Indian manufacturing industries, the evidence shows that domestic firms with weaker technological capabilities compared to foreign firms face greater difficulty in benefiting from the presence of FDI.

1.6 The Technology Gap

Several previous studies (Findlay 1978; Wang and Blomström 1992; Smeets 2008) argue that a large technology gap between FDI and local firms can be beneficial for the latter, as it increases their potential for catching up. In contrast (Blalock and Gertler 2009), suggest that if the technology gap between MNCs and domestic firms is either too wide or too narrow, local firms may be unable to absorb positive FDI spillovers.

Using a balanced panel of firm-level data on the manufacturing industry in France, Italy, and Spain during 1992–1997, (Castellani, & Antonello Zanfei 2003), examined the impact of foreign presence on the productivity of domestic enterprises. They found positive and significant externalities for Italian firms, a negative impact for Spanish firms, and no significant effects for French firms. However, their results may be influenced by productivity gaps between foreign and domestic firms as well as the absorptive capacity of local firms. The study suggests that the positive effects of FDI are correlated with a higher technology gap.

Similarly, (Chudnovsky, López, & Rossi 2004) highlight differences in the capacity of domestic firms to benefit from FDI spillovers. Firms with strong absorptive capabilities tend to acquire positive spillovers from MNCs, while those with weaker

capacities do not. The extent to which domestic firms absorb technology from MNCs depends largely on their ability and the share of skilled labor they employ. (Blalock and Gertler 2009), studying Indonesian manufacturers between 1988 and 1996, found that firms with highly educated employees and higher investments in research and development (R&D) gained more technological benefits from foreign entrants than other firms.

1.7 The Casual Relationship between FDI, DI and Economic Growth

According to (Olofsdotter 1998; Borensztein et al. 1998; Johnson, 2006), the causal relationship between FDI and economic growth depends on a country's economic conditions, political environment, and cultural factors. For instance, the level of economic development, the productivity of FDI, and government policies regulating FDI all play key roles. Moreover, the linkages between FDI and growth vary across countries depending on their stage of development (Kurtishi-Kastrati, 2013). (Lean & Tan 2011), examined the dynamic relationship between FDI, DI, and economic growth in Malaysia during 1970–2009. Their results show that FDI, DI, and economic growth are cointegrated in the long run. Specifically, FDI positively influences economic growth, while DI negatively affects it. Furthermore, an increase in FDI stimulates DI.

Similarly, (Seng, 2017), analyzed the causal relationship between FDI and economic growth in Cambodia during 1980–2014, using a Granger causality test based on a vector error correction model. The findings reveal strong evidence that FDI positively impacts Cambodia's GDP. However, the reverse causality—from GDP to FDI—was not confirmed.

(Choe, 2003) studied 80 countries between 1971–1995 using a panel VAR model to analyze the causal relationship between FDI, DI, and economic growth. His results indicate that FDI Granger-causes growth and vice versa, with stronger effects from growth to FDI than the reverse. Moreover, DI does not Granger-cause growth, though growth strongly Granger-causes DI. This implies that the observed positive correlation between economic growth and FDI inflows or DI does not necessarily mean that high FDI inflows or investment rates automatically generate rapid economic growth.

(Hong, 2014), re-examined the impact of FDI on China's economic growth using dynamic panel data from 254 prefecture-level cities during 1994–2010. The study shows that FDI has a positive impact on economic development. Factors such as economic scale, human capital, infrastructure, wage levels, and regional characteristics interact positively with FDI, mutually reinforcing output growth in the adjustment process. However, trade openness does not significantly induce FDI or contribute directly to growth, and government expenditure appears to slow growth.

Numerous empirical studies have tested the relationship between FDI and growth, with particular attention to long-run causality. However, the results remain inconclusive and mixed. While many studies suggest a robust relationship between FDI and growth, the evidence is highly heterogeneous across countries. On average, FDI does have an impact on growth in a general causal sense (Lean 2008). For instance, (Harzer et al. 2008) argue that in most developing countries, there is no clear unidirectional long-run causality running from FDI to GDP.

Liangshu (Qi 2007) investigated the significance, direction, and nature of the long- and short-run causal relationships between growth, DI, and FDI across 47 developed and developing economies during 1970–2003, using an error correction model (ECM). The results show that FDI and economic growth are unlikely to be cointegrated without including DI in the system, due to differing levels of integration between the two variables. Therefore, excluding DI may obscure the long-run relationship. The findings suggest that the causal links between growth, investment, and FDI differ significantly between developed and developing countries:

1. In developed countries, long-run equilibrium relationships are less likely to be significant than in developing countries;
2. In developed countries, causality usually runs unidirectionally—from growth to investment, from growth to FDI, or from investment to FDI. In contrast, in developing countries, causality often runs in both directions;
3. In developed countries, the causal relationships between growth and investment or between investment and FDI are generally positive. However, in developing countries, these relationships can sometimes be negative.

These results suggest that in developed economies, growth driven by innovation tends to stimulate DI and attract FDI. With strong market systems and stable macroeconomic environments, growth and DI are less dependent on FDI inflows. By

contrast, in developing economies with scarce capital, underdeveloped markets, and unstable macroeconomic conditions, FDI inflows play a more influential role in promoting both DI and growth (Liangshu Qi 2007; Elboiashi, 2011).

To summarize, Figure 1.1 illustrates the causal relationships between FDI, DI, and economic growth. According to Luo Changyuan (2007), there are three main channels through which FDI affects growth:

Summarizing, the figure 1.1 may illustrate the casually relationship between FDI, DI and economic growth. There are three channels for the FDI affecting economic growth according to LUO Changyuan. (2007):

1. Direct effect: FDI directly contributes to growth through the investment channel (I).
2. Indirect effect via DI: FDI influences growth by affecting DI, either through crowding-in or crowding-out effects ($III^* + II^*$)
3. Indirect effect via technology spillovers: FDI promotes growth by enhancing technological progress in host economies, generating positive externalities ($III + IV^*$), or by crowding in DI through linkage effects ($III^* + IV + IV^*$).

Figure 0-1 the circular flow of the dynamic relationship between FDI, GDP and DI¹

¹ Source: LUO Changyuan. (2007). FDI, domestic capital and economic growth: evidence from panel data at china's provincial level. *中国经济学前沿*, 2(1), 92-113.

Table 0-1- Summary of the impact of FDI on domestic investment and economic growth in the host country

Authors	Type of data	Sample	Variables	Main Results
Van loo (1997)	Time series	Canada;1948;1966	FDI inflow; GFCF(DI)	Crowding in Effects
Noorzory (1979)	Quarterly data	Canada;1957.1-1971.IV	FDI inflow; GCF (DI)	Crowding in effects
Borensztein et al.(1998)	Cross-section	69 developing countries; 1970-1989	FDI/GDP; growth rate of per capita real GDP; Total fixed investment (DI)	Positive effect of FDI on growth but magnitude Depends on availability of host country human capital. FDI crowding-in DI.
De Mello (1999)	Panel data and time series	32 developed and developing countries; 1970-1990	FDI inflow, TFP growth, capital accumulation (DI)	The positive impact of FDI on economic growth depends on crowding-in effect of FDI.
Agosin and Mayer (2000)	Panel data	Group of 32 countries (12 in Africa, 8 in Asia and 12	FDI/GDP, growth rate of GDP,	Strong crowding-in effect in Asia, neutral effect in Africa and strong crowding-out effect in

		in Latin America); 1970- 1996	GFCF (DI)/GDP	Latin America
Chakraborty and Basu (2002)	Time series cointegration	India; 1974-1996	Real GDP, FDI inflows	The causality runs more from GDP to FDI. FDI has negative insignificant impact on economic growth in the short-run.
Kim and Seo (2003)	Time series cointegration	Korea; 1985-1999	FDI inflow, GFCF (DI) and growth rate of GDP	Strong positive effect from growth rate of GDP to FDI rather than the effect of FDI on economic growth. FDI inflows crowd-in DI.
Choe (2003)	Panel data	Group of 80 developed and developing countries; 1971- 1995	Growth rate of per capita GDP, FDI/GDP, GFCF (DI)/GDP	FDI Granger causes economic growth and vice versa, but this effect is more apparent from growth to FDI. Unidirectional causality runs from growth to DI.
Apergis et al. (2006)	Panel cointegration data	Group of 30 countries from Asia, Africa, America	FDI inflows, GFCF (DI)	Crowding in effect of FDI for Asia and Africa. Crowding out effect for America and Europe.

		and Europe; 1992-2002		
Hansen and Rand (2006)	Panel cointegration	31 developing countries; 1970-2000	FDI/GDP, real GDP, FDI/GCF	Strong causal link from FDI ratio to GDP, also the changes in the FDI ratio cause changes in the level of GDP in the long-run. GDP Granger causes FDI, but no impact on the long-run level of the FDI ratio. Also, FDI/GCF Granger causes GDP.
Johnson (2006)	Cross-section and panel data	Group of 90 developed and developing countries; 1980- 2002	Inward stock of FDI per capita, growth rate of real GDP per capita	FDI inflows enhance economic growth in developing countries but not in developed countries.
Fedderke and Romm (2006)	Time series	South Africa; 1956- 2003	Real GDP, private sector fixed capital stock (DI), real FDI	FDI inflow crowds-in DI in the long-run but it crowds-out DI in the short-run. FDI inflow into South

				Africa is horizontal rather than vertical.
Frimpong and Oteng-Abayie (2006)	Time series data	Ghana; 1970-2002	FDI inflows, growth rate of GDP	There is no causality between FDI and GDP growth but FDI caused GDP growth during the (1984-2002) period.
Baharumshah and Thanoon 2006	Dynamic panel data	Group of 8 East Asian countries; 1982-2001	GDP, long-term debt/GDP, short-term debt/GDP, FDI/GDP, domestic savings/GDP	Domestic saving has a positive impact on the long-term economic growth. FDI influence on growth is much higher than domestic. Short-term capital inflow has adverse effect on the economic growth.
Elfakhani and Matar (2007)	Panel data	Group of 19 MENA countries; 1990-2000	FDI/GDP, growth rate of real GDP, GFCF (DI)	FDI crowds-in DI. Economic growth has a negative correlation with FDI inflows.
Tang et al. (2008)	Time series cointegration	China; 1988-2003	FDI inflows, GCF (DI), GDP	Bi-directional causality between DI and GDP. Unidirectional causality from FDI to GDP and DI. FDI crowds-in DI.

Herzer et al. (2008)	Cointegration time series	Group of 28 countries (10 in Latin American, 9 in Asia and 9 in Africa)	FDI inflow/GDP, GDP	Weak evidence for FDI effects on GDP. Weak evidence for the growth effects of FDI depend on host country conditions.
Ndikumana (2008)	Cross-section	Group of 38 sub- Saharan African countries	FDI/GDP, growth rate of GDP, Private investment/GDP	Economic growth has a positive impact on FDI. Bidirectional causality between FDI and DI, and FDI crowds-in DI. Also, FDI enhances economic growth through capital accumulation.
Adams (2009)	Pooled timeseries Cross-section	Group of 42 Sub- Saharan African countries; 1990- 2003	Growth rate of real GDP per capita, FDI inflows/GDP, GFCF (DI)/GDP	DI has a positive impact on economic growth but FDI is positive and significant only in the OLS estimation. FDI has an initial negative impact on DI.
Acar et al. 2012	Generalized Method of Moments (GMM)	From the MENA region; 1980-2008	GFCF; FDI; trade	FDI crowd out domestic investment

Ivanović (2015)	Quarterly time series data; Q12001-Q42014	Republic of Croatia	GFCF;FDI; GDP	FDI have negative influence on domestic investment

CHAPTER 2 FDI AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN CAPE VERDE

2.1 Country Overviews

Figure 2-1 Cape Verde Islands Map

The archipelago of Cape Verde (also referred to as the Cape Verde Islands or simply Cape Verde) (Figure 2.1) is a group of islands located in the Atlantic Ocean, nearly 400 miles off the western coast of Africa. The islands were discovered by Portuguese navigators in 1460 and gained independence in 1975. The country is composed of ten islands and eight islets, divided into two main groups: Barlavento, consisting of Sal, Boa Vista, Santa Luzia, Santo Antão, São Nicolau, and São Vicente; and Sotavento, consisting of Brava, Fogo, Maio, and Santiago.

Cape Verde has an estimated resident population of around 525,000 inhabitants. Despite its arid climate and mountainous terrain, the country has been developing rapidly through international cooperation and, in particular, its flourishing tourism industry. To further encourage tourism flows, successive governments have made efforts to position the islands as a regional hub for trade and transport.

Cape Verde is a sovereign, unitary, and democratic state, governed by domestic laws that safeguard human rights, peace, and justice. In addition to its legal system, Cape

Verde is party to various international conventions and treaties on human rights and sovereignty. The state is founded on principles of ideological freedom, democracy (political, social, cultural, religious, and economic), equality, justice, and solidarity.

Although Cape Verde has limited natural resources—mainly its sea, white sand, marine resources (still underexploited), wind energy, solar energy, salt, and limestone—successive governments have increasingly sought foreign investment as a key driver of future economic growth. The country actively aims to attract investment that stimulates business activities and modernizes its economic structure.

2.1.1 An Economic Overview

After gaining independence in 1975, Cape Verde faced a critical economic situation, which required successive governments to implement a series of policies and economic measures to stabilize the country. From the 1990s, the country adopted a multiparty political system and pursued programs aimed at economic liberalization and privatization. These reforms became crucial drivers for relatively rapid economic development, although domestic income growth remained uneven, with some rural and coastal areas lagging behind urban centers in terms of growth and poverty reduction.

Cape Verde officially left the list of least developed countries in 2007, a milestone attributed to good governance, openness to trade, increased integration into the global economy, and the implementation of effective social development policies. According to the African Economic Outlook (2017), the country's real GDP growth has been moderate over the past years. Between 2000 and 2008, Cape Verde recorded an average growth rate of 6.6%, before experiencing a recession in 2009 due to the European financial crisis.

Despite implementing counter-cyclical policies with high investment spending, the economy grew by only an average of 1.3% during 2010–2015. In 2016, the economy showed signs of recovery, with GDP growth reaching an estimated 3.2%, compared to 1.5% in 2015. Growth was projected at 3.7% and 4.1% for 2017 and 2018, respectively, driven by increased confidence, stronger agricultural output, a flourishing tourism sector, and ongoing government reforms.

The 2008 global financial crisis, followed by the European debt crisis (Europe being Cape Verde's major multilateral partner), had a negative impact on the country, leading to sharp declines in foreign direct investment (FDI), exports, tourism, and remittances from migrants. Nevertheless, after a recession in 2009, the economy resumed growth, averaging 1.3% between 2010 and 2015, as shown in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2-2 Economic situation of Vape Verde. Constructed by author from IMF data base

However, in response to the global financial crisis and the European debt crisis, Cape Verde engaged in counter-cyclical spending to maintain growth. As a result, by 2016, the country's debt level had expanded to an estimated 125% of GDP. For example, the overall budget deficit reached 8.9% in 2013 and 7.5% in 2014. In light of these debt pressures, the government implemented measures to consolidate public finances through austerity policies. By 2015, the overall deficit had been reduced to 4.1%, compared to the originally budgeted 7.9%, and continued to narrow to 3.3% of GDP in 2016 (African Economic Outlook, 2017).

The reduction in the deficit was primarily due to an increase in revenues resulting from the expansion of the tax base. At the same time, the public investment program contributed to the improvement of fiscal balances, with investment spending falling from 10.2% of GDP in 2013 to 3.5% in 2016. Over the medium to long term, the government has been adjusting economic policies to foster stronger economic growth

in Cape Verde. These measures include offering greater incentives to foreign investors, encouraging private investment, and improving the overall business environment.

2.1.2 Private Business Sector Overview

The Cape Verdean private sector is nascent and is largely dominated by micro-, small-, and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Most of these enterprises still face significant constraints, particularly in accessing bank loans, due to their limited ability to provide collateral acceptable to financial institutions. In 2009, to foster entrepreneurship, the government established the Agency for the Development of Enterprises and Innovation (ADEI). Since its creation, ADEI has promoted investment in SMEs, assisted entrepreneurs in designing business plans, and provided training in areas such as marketing and financial management.

According to the National Institute of Statistics (INE), in 2016 the Cape Verdean business sector comprised approximately 9,444 active companies, an increase of 87 compared to 2015, representing growth of 0.9%. The sector employed 55,884 people, 3,101 more than in 2015, corresponding to a 5.9% increase. The hotel and restaurant sector contributed significantly to this growth, with employment rising by 1,862 people, a positive evolution of 18.7% compared to 2015.

The commerce sector concentrated the largest share of companies (46.3%) and employment (23.3%), and contributed the most to turnover (36.0%). The hotel and catering sector was the second largest in terms of companies (15.1%) and employment (21.2%), and ranked second in turnover contribution (11.9%).

Business activity is unevenly distributed across the islands. The islands of Santiago, São Vicente, Sal, and Boa Vista accounted for about 78.4% of all active companies in 2016, 91.8% of total employment, and 97.0% of total business turnover in the Cape Verdean economy, highlighting a significant geographic concentration of private sector activity.

2.1.3 Business Environment

Since the 1990s, Cape Verde has made significant advances in improving its business environment, particularly in fiscal and regulatory policy, administrative services and procedures, modernization of public administration, human capital investment, and substantial economic infrastructure development.

Key reforms include measures to facilitate the country's accession to the World Trade Organization (WTO), simplification of business licensing, property registration, and business liquidation procedures. Furthermore, Cape Verde is now a member of numerous international organizations, such as the United Nations (UN), European Union (EU), World Bank (WB), International Monetary Fund (IMF), European Investment Bank (EIB), African Development Bank (ADB), Millennium Challenge Corporation (MCC), and the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), offering a broad potential for investors.

Cape Verde is also recognized as one of the most stable and well-governed countries in Africa. It has received several awards and rankings for competitiveness, democracy, and freedom. According to the Freedom House Report (2017), Cape Verde is classified in the highest category for civil and political freedoms, making it the freest country in Africa. In addition, it ranks 3rd in Africa for good governance (Ibrahim Index of African Governance, 2017), 23rd globally in democracy, and 1st among Lusophone countries (Index of Democracy, 2016). Such recognition is crucial in enhancing the business environment, although challenges remain at both macroeconomic and microeconomic levels.

For instance, the World Economic Forum (WEF) ranked Cape Verde 110th out of 138 countries in global competitiveness for 2016–17, indicating considerable room for improvement in labor market efficiency, financial market development, business sophistication, innovation, and related areas.

2.1.4 Doing Business in Cape Verde

Cape Verde is a country characterized by social, political, and economic stability and peace, with strong international relations, strategic partnerships, and global

recognition. These factors build confidence among individuals, companies, governments, and international financial institutions.

Over the last decade, Cape Verde has made considerable progress in improving its business environment. Reforms have simplified the process of starting a business and strengthened labor regulations, including reducing the maximum duration of fixed-term contracts, increasing paid annual leave, introducing retraining or reassignment obligations, and extending the notice period in cases of redundancy. Additionally, the country has improved insolvency resolution by adopting a law that introduces a reorganization procedure, facilitates the continuation of the debtor's business, and allows creditors greater participation in key decisions during insolvency proceedings, among other reforms (World Bank Doing Business, 2018).

The impacts of these reforms are reflected in measures designed to enhance national economic competitiveness and contribute to sustainable economic growth at all levels. According to the World Bank Doing Business 2017 report, Cape Verde was ranked 129th out of 190 economies in ease of doing business. Following the reforms introduced in 2018, Cape Verde's ranking improved to 127th. The country performs relatively well in certain areas, such as contract enforcement (43rd), property registration (71st), and starting a business (98th). However, challenges remain in other areas, including electricity access (145th), protecting minority investors (164th), and resolving insolvency (168th), as shown in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2-3 Rankings on Doing Business Topics- Cape Verde 2018. Source: World Bank Doing Business

2.1.5 The Mains Sectors of Investment (Business Opportunity)

Cape Verde’s government is widely regarded as one of the most stable and democratic in Sub-Saharan Africa. It is a society based on laws that respect human rights and civil liberties, including a free press. Due to its strategic location between Africa, Europe, and the Americas, Cape Verde has historically served as a trade hub—first as a center for the slave trade and later, in the twentieth century, as a shipping port.

Today, Cape Verde has a services-based economy, with the tourism sector driving much of the country’s economic growth. The high potential to attract tourists presents significant investment opportunities in tourism and related infrastructure, such as transport and facilities, especially to improve connectivity between the islands.

The economy also faces constraints due to a weak natural resource base and recurring droughts, leading to serious water shortages. Approximately 82% of food is imported, creating opportunities in agriculture and agro-business. Additionally, the fishing sector, particularly lobster and tuna, remains underexploited.

The financial sector is small and limited, with the two largest commercial banks—Banco Comercial do Atlântico (BCA) and Caixa Económica de Cabo Verde—now controlled by Portuguese banks. Microbusinesses face significant challenges in accessing finance, relying mainly on microfinance institutions. This gap represents another potential area for investment.

Other sectors offering investment opportunities include energy and renewable energy, light manufacturing, and services. While these are the principal growth sectors, Cape Verde offers a wide range of other opportunities, and investors are warmly welcomed.

2.1.6 The Main Challenges and Opportunities

Since its independence in 1975, Cape Verde has made notable progress, achieving good governance, social peace, political stability, essential economic infrastructure, reasonable levels of human development, sound macroeconomic management, a favorable geographic location along key trade routes, and international credibility.

Despite these gains, several challenges remain. Globalization and trade liberalization have increased competition, and the emerging world has become more competitive. Given its limited natural resources, Cape Verde must rely heavily on innovation, institutional development, and the strengthening of firms and services. Building indigenous technological capacity and continually improving human capital, infrastructure, and institutional frameworks are essential for sustaining development and competing in the global economy.

Cape Verde is structurally vulnerable due to its small size, insularity, and exposure to unfavorable natural endowments. Mitigating these vulnerabilities requires strategies to enhance competitiveness, such as promoting innovation and R&D, diversifying the economy, and fully exploiting natural resources like marine and renewable energy potential.

One of the most critical constraints facing the economy is the cost and reliability of inter-island transportation, which remains a major barrier to the movement of people and goods. Addressing this constraint through targeted policy interventions is crucial for sustaining growth and enabling Cape Verde to compete in the global economy.

2.2 Foreign Direct Investment in Cape Verde: Overview

As previously mentioned, since the 1990s, Cape Verde adopted a multiparty political system and implemented programs for economic liberalization and privatization. These reforms had a significant impact on the economy and helped attract foreign investors. Successive governments have actively sought to attract foreign investment through tax exemptions and incentives, believing that FDI can help diversify the economy, enhance growth, and strengthen the business environment.

However, the growth of FDI has been irregular. Initially, it gained momentum with the opening of the economy to private investment, followed by growth in the tourism sector, which began with real estate purchases. Peaks in net FDI inflows corresponded to waves of privatization of the country's largest companies, particularly in telecommunications (1995), water, and finance (1999). The electricity company Electra returned to government ownership in 2010.

Due to Cape Verde's special partnership with the European Union, most FDI originates from the Eurozone. Between 1986 and 2010, FDI inflows averaged approximately 4.5% of GDP (Figure 2.4). The dynamics of FDI are mainly driven by the tourism sector, which receives roughly 90% of foreign direct investment, making it a critical driver of economic growth and employment generation.

Figure 2-4 Net inflows of foreign direct investment in Cape Verde. Constructed by author from UNCTAD database

2.2.1- Tourism sector

Tourism is a key factor for Cape Verde's economic growth. Between 2000 and 2012, the number of tourist arrivals increased significantly, from 145,076 to 533,877, while overnight stays rose from 162,095 to 3,332,275. In 2012, for the first time in history, tourism inflows (533,877 visitors) exceeded the country's resident population.

Sal Island has consistently been the most popular destination. The largest source of tourists is the United Kingdom, accounting for 20.5% of all visitors, followed by Portugal (15.4%), Germany (9.5%), Cape Verdean residents (8.4%), and Wales (8.3%). Regarding overnight stays, the United Kingdom also ranks first with 31.8%, followed by Portugal (12.9%), Germany (11.3%), and Wales (9.2%) (Figure 2.5). Figure 2.6 shows net FDI inflows into the tourism sector in millions of Cape Verdean Escudos (CVE).

Figure 2-5 Evolutions of tourist demand in Cape Verde according to the main countries. From INE 2016

Figure 2-6 FDI by tourism sector (millions of CPVE)². Constructed by actor from back of Cape Verde (BCV).

2.3 Absorptive Capacity of Domestic Companies in Cape Verde (Evidence)

As mentioned in the previous chapter, the effects of FDI on domestic investment (DI) can be positive, through crowding in domestic investment, or negative, through crowding out. However, researchers suggest that these effects largely depend on the absorptive capacity of the country or domestic firms to capture FDI spillovers. Specific policies to improve host country absorptive capacity are also recommended.

Following studies by (Nguyen et al. 2009; Hermes and Lensink 2003; Alffaro et al. 2004), firm characteristics such as size and market orientation play a critical role in determining absorptive capacity. Boly, Coniglio, Prota, & Seric, (2015), show that the effects of FDI inflows on DI in Sub-Saharan Africa are highly heterogeneous: larger and more productive domestic firms benefit more from interactions with multinational corporations (MNCs).

2.3.1 Technology and innovations

Economic development is strongly influenced by innovation and scientific research, which drive economic and social change. The National Institute of Statistics (INE) conducted a survey on business innovation and research during 2013–2014.

² CPVE-Escudos Cabo-Verdianos

The study covered companies, higher education institutions, and research institutions, aiming to collect information on product, process, organizational, and marketing innovations. Among 3,067 companies registered under the IV Business Registration (IV-RE), 201 reported engaging in innovation activities. In 2015, a survey was applied to these companies: 120 reported having conducted innovation activities during 2013–2014, while 81 did not.

The sectoral results show that the most significant innovations occurred in wholesale trade and retail, as well as in the repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles, representing:

Table 2-1 technology and Innovations in the country. Source INE

	Total	%
Total companies with organized accounting	3067	100
Companies engaged in Innovation Activities	120	3,9%
Products innovations	78	2,5%
Process Innovation	67	2,2%
Organizational Innovation	66	2,2%
Marketing Innovation	72	2,3%

- Product innovations: 30.8%
- Process innovations: 33.3%
- Organizational innovations: 29.2%
- Marketing innovations: 32.4%

In the manufacturing sector, innovations represented:

- Product: 19.2%
- Process: 21.2%

- Organizational: 16.9%
- Marketing: 21.1%

Larger companies were more likely to engage in innovation than smaller firms. Among small enterprises, process and organizational innovations were most common, at 58.2% and 50.0%, respectively.

2.3.1.1 Product Innovations and Process

Product innovation includes activities related to research and development (R&D), acquisition of machinery, equipment, software, and buildings, as well as acquisition of existing knowledge, training, marketing, and design. Innovations may be developed internally, in partnership with other organizations, or externally by another institution. Among 78 companies involved in product innovation, 68% reported developing the innovation internally, 25.6% in partnership, and 17.9% externally.

2.3.1.2 Process Innovation

Process innovation refers to the implementation of new or significantly improved production or distribution methods, including changes in techniques, equipment, or software (e.g., maintenance, operations, accounting, computing). Innovations must be new to the company but do not need to be new to the industry. Among 67 companies conducting process innovation in 2013–2014, 50.7% involved new distribution methods, while 44% involved new production or manufacturing methods.

2.3.1.4 Organizational Innovation

Organizational innovation involves new methods in business practices, workplace organization, or external relations, resulting from strategic decisions. Mergers and acquisitions are excluded. Among 66 companies (2.2% of the total), new management systems and significant organizational changes were the main contributors to organizational innovation.

2.3.1.5 Marketing innovation

Marketing innovation refers to implementing new concepts or strategies that differ from previous methods, such as changes in product design, packaging, distribution, or pricing. Routine or seasonal changes are excluded. Among 72 companies (2.2%), new pricing policies for products and services were the main contributors to marketing innovation in Cape Verde.

2.3.2 Human Capital

Human capital is one of the most crucial factors in a country's competitiveness and its capacity to sustain growth. In a global economic context, the success of a national economy depends on the skills, energy, and creativity of its people. As an open economy with ambitions to compete globally, Cape Verde currently faces evolving human capital needs, which require not only general skills but also advanced and specialized competencies (African Development Report, 2012).

Given the country's scarcity of natural resources, the government has prioritized human capital as a key driver of economic development. Since independence, education policies have focused on improving the education system and building human capacity. Education accounts for one of the largest shares of public expenditure, second only to infrastructure. Approximately 20% of the annual budget is allocated to education. Cape Verde boasts one of the highest literacy rates in Africa, with around 90% of the population over age 15 being literate, and about 25% holding a university degree. Additionally, around 250 new graduates have earned doctoral degrees across various academic fields (Branco, 2016).

The country also performs well in terms of school life expectancy, estimated at 12 years in 2009 from primary to tertiary education, among the highest in Africa. Despite these gains, challenges remain, particularly regarding the quality and types of human capital most suited to the country's development goals.

In Cape Verde, the service sector employs the largest number of workers, but most are unskilled. There is a mismatch between the labor market's needs and the areas of expertise produced by the education system. Currently, no explicit policy or incentive

structure exists to align study programs with priority areas for skills development according to the Agenda for Transformation or projected labor force needs (Brito, 2013)

2.4 Analyses and Conclusion

The process of innovation in Cape Verdean enterprises is still at a developing stage. Companies with organized accounting systems are attempting to implement innovation activities, while companies without such systems show a total deficit in innovation.

These findings highlight the need to cultivate a culture of innovation across products, processes, organizational methods, and marketing. Government support and encouragement from other entities are essential to strengthen this culture. Cape Verdean companies have the potential to produce indicators of performance that are competitive with firms in Sub-Saharan Africa and globally.

Many previous studies indicate that the absorptive capacity of domestic firms depends heavily on innovation and R&D. For example, Cohen & Levinthal (1990), Xiaolan Fu (2008), Nguyen et al. (2009), and Murovec & Prodan (2009) emphasize that R&D and innovation processes are central to a firm's ability to absorb knowledge and technology. Once this capacity is developed, domestic firms can more effectively capture FDI spillovers.

Blalock and Gertler (2009), in a study of Indonesian manufacturers from 1988 to 1996, found that firms with highly educated employees and investments in R&D received greater technology benefits from foreign entrants. This evidence highlights the weak absorptive capacity of many Cape Verdean firms and underscores the need for government efforts to support innovation and R&D. Strengthening local firms in this way is essential for boosting the country's economic growth.

CHAPTER 3 METHODOLOGY SPECIFICATIONS

3.1 Autoregressive Distributed Lags (ADRL) and Bound Test For Co-Integration

Cointegration refers to the existence of a specific stationary linear combination of variables that are individually non-stationary but integrated of order $I(d)$. Econometrically, cointegration captures the existence of a long-run equilibrium among economic time series, which, despite short-term fluctuations, tend to converge over time. Establishing cointegration provides a strong statistical and economic basis for employing an error correction model (ECM), which incorporates both short-run dynamics and long-run relationships.

The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach to cointegration is widely used to identify cointegrating vectors. In this framework, each underlying variable contributes to the long-run relationship. A distributed lag model simply means that unrestricted lags of regressors are included in the regression function. This testing procedure explicitly determines whether the variables under study are cointegrated, given the endogenous variable.

In this study, the ARDL cointegration technique developed by Pesaran & Shin (1998) and Pesaran et al. (2001) has been applied to examine both short-run and long-run relationships among the variables. The choice of ARDL is motivated by its several advantages over other cointegration techniques. As highlighted by Belloumi (2014) and Ameer & Xu (2017), ARDL estimators of long-run coefficients are super-consistent even in small sample sizes. Moreover, ARDL can be applied regardless of whether variables are integrated of order $I(0)$, $I(1)$, or a mixture of both.

The ECM can be derived from the ARDL through a simple linear transformation, capturing short-run adjustments toward long-run equilibrium without losing long-run information. This requires including a sufficient number of lags to reflect the data-generating process within a general-to-specific modeling framework.

Another advantage of ARDL is that it produces unbiased long-run estimates (Harris & Sollis, 2003). In addition, only a single ARDL equation needs to be estimated, unlike the Johansen approach, which requires estimating a system of equations. Importantly,

ARDL allows different lag lengths to be specified for each variable, making it more flexible than the Johansen method.

The ARDL modeling framework can be expressed as follows:

$$\Delta \ln Y_t = \alpha_{0y} + \sum_{i=1}^n B_{iy} \Delta \ln Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n C_{iy} \Delta \ln X_{t-1} + \phi_{1y} \Delta \ln Y_{t-1} + \phi_{2y} \Delta \ln X_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{1t} \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta \ln X_t = \alpha_{0x} + \sum_{i=1}^n B_{ix} \Delta \ln X_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n C_{ix} \Delta \ln Y_{t-1} + \omega_{1x} \Delta \ln X_{t-1} + \omega_{2x} \Delta \ln Y_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{2t} \quad (2)$$

Where:

Δ is the difference operator, Y_t is the log of the dependent variable, X_t is the log of independent variable and ε_{1t} , and ε_{2t} are serially independent random errors with mean zero and finite covariance matrix. (See Jenkins, & Katircioglu, (2010).

when Y as a dependent variable, the null hypothesis of no co-integration is, $H_0: \phi_{1y} = \phi_{2y} = 0$, against the alternative hypotheses of co-integration, $H_1: \phi_{1y} \neq \phi_{2y} \neq 0$. On the other hand, when X is a dependent variable the null hypothesis of no co-integration is $H_0: \omega_{1x} = \omega_{2x} = 0$, against the alternative hypotheses of co-integration given as $H_1: \omega_{1x} \neq \omega_{2x} \neq 0$.

The null hypothesis of no cointegration is not rejected when the F-statistic is below the lower critical bound (LCB). Cointegration is confirmed if the F-statistic exceeds the upper critical bound (UCB). If the statistic lies between the two bounds, the result is inconclusive.

the ARDL framework allows estimation of both the short-run and long-run effects of FDI on domestic investment. Specifically, the model is used to evaluate the extent of “crowding in” or “crowding out” effects. Following Agosin & Machado and Mody & Murshid (2005): Crowding out occurs when domestic investment grows less than the increase in FDI (coefficient of FDI < 1); and crowding in occurs when domestic investment rises more than the increase in FDI (coefficient of FDI > 1).

Furthermore, is not rejected The null hypothesis of no cointegration when the F-statistics is less than the lower critical bound value (LCB) and there is cointegration if F-statistics is greater than the upper critical bound value. Otherwise, the cointegration test is inconclusive.

From the long-run and short-run DI model is estimated the magnitude of the crowd in and crowd out of FDI on domestic investment. Accordingly, FDI might stimulate domestic investment (crowding in) or displace domestic investment (crowd out effects). Following (Agosin and Machado and Mody and Murshid 2005), crowd out take place when DI grow less than the increase in FDI, that is, the coefficient of FDI less than 1 (one). Conversely, the crowd in effects occurs when the rise in DI is higher than the increase in FDI, leading to the increase of the coefficient of FDI more than 1(one).

3.2 EViews 10

To conduct the tests, this study employs the software **EViews 10**. EViews is one of the leading macroeconomic forecasting and analysis tools used worldwide. In addition, it is particularly well-suited for researchers working with time series, cross-sectional, or longitudinal data.

EViews allows users to manage data quickly and efficiently, perform econometric and statistical analyses, generate forecasts and model simulations, and produce high-quality graphs and tables suitable for publication or inclusion in other applications

3.3 Date and Variables

The empirical analysis is based on yearly time series data covering the period 1986–2015, obtained from UNCTAD (United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, 2017). UNCTAD compiles, validates, and disseminates a wide range of data collected from both national and international sources. Most of its time series cover the long term, with some dating back to 1948, for nearly all economies

worldwide. This breadth allows researchers to analyze emerging and urgent issues within the framework of long-term trends and broad geographical scope.

GDP is used as the growth rate of GDP per capita;

DI (Domestic Investment) is used as a proxy for GFCF (Gross Fixed Capital Formation) widely used measure in the literature;

FDI is measured as a percentage of GDP

From the DI Model, DI is used to assess the influence of FDI on domestic investment. As noted earlier, FDI can have both positive and negative effects on DI, depending on the magnitude of crowding-in or crowding-out. GDP growth is also included to estimate the impact of per capita growth on stimulating domestic investment in the Cape Verdean economy.

From the FDI Model, both GDP and DI are included to evaluate their role in attracting FDI inflows.

From the GDP Model, the variables FDI and DI are used to estimate their influence on promoting growth.

3.2 Unit Root

Before running causality tests among the time series variables, it is necessary to check the stationarity of the data. The ARDL model for co-integration can only be estimated if the variables are integrated of order I(0), I(1), or a combination of both, but not I(2).

A unit root occurs when one or more characteristic roots of a process are equal to one. The simplest model that may contain a unit root is the AR(1) model, given by:

$$Y_t = \phi Y_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

Where:

Where ε_t denotes a serially uncorrected white noise error term with a mean of zero and a constant Variance. If $\phi = 1$, the equation reduces to a random walk without drift, i.e., a nonstationary process. This situation is referred to as the unit root problem, meaning the series is nonstationary. Conversely, if $\phi < 1$, the series Y_t is stationary.

Stationarity is important because correlations can persist in nonstationary time series even in large samples, which may lead to spurious regression. The unit root problem can be solved, or stationarity achieved, by differencing the data set (see Ssekuma, 2011). Therefore, the analysis tests the null hypothesis that all variables contain unit roots against the alternative that they do not, both at levels and in first differences. To determine stationarity and the order of integration, the study applies the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test (Dickey & Fuller, 1979) and the Phillips-Perron (PP) test (Phillips & Perron, 1988).

3.2.1 The Results for Unit Root Test

The results of testing Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), Domestic Investment (DI), and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) tests are presented in Tables 3.1 and 3.2, respectively. A visual plot is provided in Appendix 1.

Based on the ADF statistics, the test values for DI, FDI, and GDP do not exceed the critical values at the 5% level of significance. This indicates that the variables are not stationary at their levels. Similarly, the PP test confirms that the series for DI, FDI, and GDP are also non-stationary at levels, as the test statistics fail to exceed their corresponding critical values at the 5% significance level.

Overall, both the ADF and PP tests consistently fail to reject the null hypothesis of a unit root in the level form of the variables at the 10%, 5%, and 1% significance levels. Consequently, the variables were re-examined at their first differences. At this stage, the results of both tests show that the statistics exceed the critical values at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis of a unit root. This demonstrates that FDI, DI, and GDP become stationary after first differencing.

Therefore, the three variables are integrated of order one, $I(1)$, which implies that they share a common long-run stochastic trend. The results confirm that the variables can be subjected to cointegration analysis to determine whether long-run relationships exist and, if so, to identify the number of cointegrating vectors among them.

Table 3-1 ADF tests for unit root tests for all variables

VARIABLES	ADF			
	Level		First difference	
	Intercept	Intercept and Trend	Intercept	Intercept and Trend
FDI	-2.039304	-3.202284	-6.697125*	-5.334554*
DI	-2.553483	-2.517880	-6.015710*	-5.902958*
GDP	-2.559971	-2.595189	-5.153543*	-5.086956*

Table 3-2 PP tests for unit root tests for all variables

VARIABLES	PP			
	Level		First difference	
	Intercept	Intercept and Trend	Intercept	Intercept and Trend
FDI	-2.039304	-3.209551	-7.957402*	-8.455594*
DI	-2.546421	-2.512280	-6.033991*	-5.919491*
GDP	-2.445076	-2.407873	-8.195569*	-9.873413*

CHAPTER 4: FINDINGS AND ANALYSES

4.1 Co-Integrations Test Results

Before testing for cointegration among the variables, it is necessary to determine the optimal lag length for the ARDL model equations. The optimal lag length can be selected using various information criteria, such as the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), the Schwarz Information Criterion (SIC), or the Hannan-Quinn Criterion (HQC). As noted by (Nkoro, & Uko 2016), identifying the appropriate lag length in an ARDL model is crucial to avoid estimation problems such as non-normal residuals, autocorrelation, or heteroscedasticity (see also Elboiashi, 2011). In practice, the

preferred model is usually the one with the lowest information criterion value or smallest standard errors (Nkoro, & Uko 2016). To this end, we estimated the equations with different lag orders and selected the specification that did not suffer from autocorrelation or heteroscedasticity issues. Several diagnostic tests were conducted to validate the specification, and the chosen model was found to be well-specified, with no evidence of serial correlation or heteroscedasticity (see Tables 4.4 and 4.5, and Figures 4.1 and 4.2).

The optimal lag length was ultimately determined using the Schwarz Information Criterion (SIC), consistent with (Elboiashi 2011), who emphasizes that SIC is particularly suitable for small sample sizes as it minimizes the loss of degrees of freedom. Similarly, (Pesaran and Shin 1998) also highlight the consistency of the Schwarz criterion in model selection with small samples.

After establishing the optimal lag, the cointegration test was performed. The results are presented in Table 4.1. When DI is treated as the dependent variable, FDI= 6.69, exceeding the upper bound critical value at the 5% significance level. This indicates evidence of a long-run relationship between DI and the explanatory variables. Similarly, when FDI is considered as the dependent variable, FFDI= 5.92, which exceeds the upper bound at the 10% significance level, suggesting cointegration at this level. By contrast, when GDP is the dependent variable, FGDP= 2.62, which falls below the corresponding upper bound critical value, and not statistically significant at levels. In this case, we fail to reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration. Thus, while DI and FDI show evidence of long-run relationships, GDP does not exhibit cointegration with the other variables under the given specification.

Table 4-1 Co-Integrations Analyses

Equations Model	F-statistics	SC lag length Criteria	Bound Critical values		Decision
			I(0)	I(1)	
FDI (FDI, GDP)	6.69**	(1, 2, 2)	4.19	5.06	Cointegrated
FGDP (DI, FDI)	2.62	(1, 0, 1)	4.87	5.85	No cointegration
FFDI (GDP, DI)	5.92***	(1, 0, 1)	6.34	7.52	Cointegrated

***Denotes statistically significant at ***10% level, ** 5% level, and * 1% level respectively

4.1.1 The Results from Domestic Investment (DI) Model

Table 4.2 reports the long-run and short-run results when DI is treated as the dependent variable.

In the long run, the coefficient of FDI is positive and statistically significant at the 1% level for the Cape Verdean economy. This implies that a 1% increase in FDI leads to more than a 1% increase in total domestic investment. The results align with several theoretical and empirical studies, particularly in the context of developing economies, which suggest that FDI stimulates domestic investment (Ndikumana & Verick, 2008; Acquah, 2017; Lean & Tan, 2011; Fedderke & Romm, 2006; Pilbeam & Oboleveciute, 2012; Ghazali, 2010). However, the findings differ from Ahmed et al. (2015), who found neutral effects in Uganda, and Polat (2017), who argued that FDI inflows do not significantly affect domestic investment.

In the **short run**, however, the lagged value of FDI has a negative and significant impact on DI at the 5% level. This suggests that a 1% increase in FDI leads to a

decrease of less than 1% in domestic investment, indicating that FDI crowds out domestic investment in the short term. Similar results are reported in other studies, such as Ivanović (2015) for Croatia, Titarenko (2005) for Latvia, and Adams (2009) for Sub-Saharan Africa. The reasons for this effect are debated. Fry (1993) argues that FDI inflows may simply substitute for other forms of capital inflows. Acar et al. (2012) note that FDI may not necessarily create new business opportunities for local firms and may instead displace them. The crowding-out effect can also stem from the stronger competitiveness of foreign firms, which benefit from advanced technologies, superior management practices, and higher productivity, forcing domestic firms to scale down or cut production (Nguyen et al., 2009; Girma & Görg, 2005).

The absorptive capacity of domestic firms is central to this discussion. Arvanitis et al. (2016) emphasize that R&D activities are critical for firms to benefit from spillovers. Similarly, Cohen and Levinthal (1990), Xiaolan Fu (2008), Nguyen et al. (2009), and Murovec & Prodan (2009) highlight that R&D and innovation are key determinants of absorptive capacity. Without sufficient investment in innovation and R&D, domestic firms may fail to capture the positive spillovers from FDI. In Cape Verde, evidence suggests weak innovation activity. From 3,067 registered companies with organized accounts, only 201 reported engaging in innovation activities, and of those, just 120 carried out innovations between 2013–2014 (product, process, organizational, or marketing innovations). This supports the argument that foreign firms, with greater technological and managerial capacities, outperform local firms, thereby crowding them out. More research is needed to better understand the absorptive capacity of Cape Verdean firms.

Following, Arvanitis, et al. (2016), the performance effects of spillovers is strongly correlated with R&D (research and development) activities developed by firms. In addition, R&D is the most channel in which companies generate and acquire technological information's. Accordingly, R&D and innovation process is one of the main factors of absorptive capacity of domestic firms. Once this level is achieved, becomes more easier the absorption of FDI spillovers. (See; Cohen, & Levinthal, (1990); Xiaolan Fu 2008); Nguyen et al (2009); Murovec, & Prodan, (2009). Here, hypothetically we strongly believe that the negative effects drive from FDI to

domestic investment in the Cape Verdean economy is due to the lack of absorptive capacity. Or, consequently due to the lack activities of technology, innovations, and R&D., on the other hand, the negative impact of FDI in domestic investment can be justified by weak or imperfect financial market. Has pointed out in a previous chapter, From 3067 companies with organized accountings in Cape Verde and registered in the scope of the IV Business Registration IV (IV-RE), 201 companies answered that had realized innovations activities. Additionally, in 2015 was applied the first questionnaires' correlated to innovations for those 201 companies. For These companies 120 have responded that they had realized the innovations activities, (products innovations, process, organizational and marketing), during the period 2013-2014 and the remaining 81 companies have not carried out any innovation activities. This support many of theoretical and empirical studies already discussed in this study, arguing that foreign firms have better capacity productivity than domestic firms and perform better. Consequently forcing domestic firms to reduce or cut their productions. However, more studies should be carried out to better understand this matters regarding the absorptive capacity of firms in Cape Verdean economy.

Regarding GDP, Table 4.2 shows that in the long run, the growth of GDP has a negative and significant effect on DI at the 1% level. Similar findings are reported by Elboiashi (2011) for Brazil and by Acar et al. (2012) for MENA countries. In the short run, however, the lagged value of GDP growth has a positive effect on DI at the 10% level, suggesting a positive correlation between changes in GDP growth and domestic investment.

The error correction term (ECT-1) is negative and significant at the 1% level, with a coefficient of -0.78 . This indicates that about 78% of the disequilibrium from the previous year is corrected within the current year, confirming the existence of a long-run equilibrium relationship among the variables. As Nkoro & Uko (2016) explain, a negative and significant ECT coefficient indicates convergence toward equilibrium, while a positive value would suggest divergence.

4.1.2 The Results from Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) Model

Regarding Table 4.3, when we assume FDI as the dependent variable in the long run, the results show that the coefficients of DI and GDP growth have a positive and significant influence on FDI at the 1% level. Despite the significance, the coefficients are less than one, demonstrating that both DI and GDP growth are drivers of foreign direct investment in the country, but the impact is not strong. For instance, the elasticity estimates indicate that a 1% increase in GDP growth and domestic investment raises FDI inflows in the long run by 0.58% and 0.21%, respectively.

These findings are consistent with several recent empirical studies on the role of GDP growth in attracting FDI (Duarte et al., 2017; Lan, 2006; Javaid, 2016; Iansiraroj & Doucouliagos, 2015). However, unlike the long-run results, the impact of GDP growth on FDI is positive but no longer statistically significant in the short run. This demonstrates that GDP growth is a significant factor for attracting FDI inflows only in the long run, and suggests that small market size does not constitute a strong determinant for FDI inflows into the country.

In contrast, the coefficient of DI in the short run is consistent with changes in FDI, indicating that domestic investment positively affects FDI inflows in Cape Verde in both the short and long run. These results align with Ndikumana and Verick (2008) and Ullah et al. (2014), but differ from Lean and Tan (2011), who highlighted that DI is a factor for attracting FDI inflows only in the short run.

Returning to Table 4.3, the ECT (-1) is negative and statistically significant, demonstrating that the equations are well specified and confirming the existence of a long-run relationship between the variables. For the FDI model, the ECT (-1) value of -0.99 indicates the speed of adjustment, suggesting that nearly all disequilibrium is corrected within a year.

To test the stability of the model, several diagnostic tests were conducted for the FDI and DI equations, including the White heteroscedasticity test, the Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM test, the Ramsey RESET test, and the CUSUM test. The results, reported in Tables 4.4 and 4.5 and Figures 4.1 and 4.2, indicate that the model residuals follow a normal distribution, with no evidence of serial correlation or

autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity. Moreover, the Ramsey RESET test confirms the model's efficiency (p-values exceeding the critical value at the 10% level). Additionally, Figures 4.1 and 4.2 illustrate the stability of the model through the cumulative sum of recursive residuals (CUSUM) and the cumulative sum of squared recursive residuals (CUSUM-squared). Following Brown et al. (1975), the results confirm that the estimated coefficients remain within the critical bounds, supporting the overall stability of the model.

Table 4-2 Long-run and short-run coefficients- DI=F (FDI, GDP)

Variables	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-statistic	P-value
GDP	-1.521741	0.501718	-3.033058	0.0068*
FDI	3.047965	0.657832	4.633349	0.0002*
Constant	44.858227	2.940418	15.255729	0.0000*

***Denotes statistically significant at ***10% level, ** 5% level, and * 1% level respectively

Short-run analyses

Variables	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-statistic	P-value
D(FDI(-1))	-0.812123	0.368984	-2.200973	0.0403**
D(FDI)	0.972012	0.350102	2.776369	0.0120*
D(GDP(-1))	0.698384	0.387702	1.801339	0.0875***
D(GDP)	0.003189	0.327169	0.009747	0.9923
ECT(-1)	-0.782051	0.186877	-4.184852	0.0005

Table 4-3 Long-run and short-run coefficients FDI =F (DI, GDP)

Variables	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-statistic	P-value
GDP	0.588562	0.148240	3.970327	0.0006*
DI	0.217012	0.074923	2.896476	0.0081*
Constant	-10.633041	2.918363	-3.643495	0.0014*

***Denotes statistically significant at ***10% level, ** 5% level, and * 1% level respectively

Short-run coefficients

Variables	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-statistic	P-value
D(GDP)	0.265724	0.160470	1.655912	0.1113
D(DI)	0.217012	0.074923	2.896476	0.0081*
ECT(-1)	-0.995124	0.201144	-4.947307	0.0001*

Table 4-4 diagnostic tests DI Model

Diagnostic test	t- statistic	probability
Ransey reset test	0.966500	0.3466
Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:	0.451976	0.5099
White Heteroscedasticity	9.107185	0.3333

Figure 4-1 Pot of CUSUM and CUSUM of squares test relative to DI Model

Table 4-5 diagnostic tests FDI Model

Diagnostic test	t- statistic	probability
Ransey reset test	1.253319	0.2232
Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:	0.330219	0.5714
White Heteroscedasticity	3.100820	0.6844

Figure 4-2 Pot of CUSUM and CUSUM of squares test relative to FDI Model

CHAPTER 5 CONCLUSION

Since the early years, Cape Verde has attracted a sizeable amount of foreign direct investment (FDI). However, as previously mentioned, research on the impact of FDI on the Cape Verdean economy remains limited, with few studies specifically examining the link between FDI and domestic investment (DI).

This thesis investigates the economic effects of FDI on DI in Cape Verde using data from 1986–2015. First, the ADF and PP tests were applied to determine whether the variables were stationary. The results showed that all variables were non-stationary, but became stationary after applying the first difference. The ARDL estimations and the bounds test for cointegration were then used to examine both short- and long-run relationships among the variables.

When GDP growth was assumed as the dependent variable, the bounds test indicated no cointegration among the variables. However, for DI and FDI as dependent variables, the results suggest that long-run relationships exist.

In the short run, results from the DI model show that FDI crowds out domestic investment: a 1% increase in FDI leads to a decline of less than 1% in DI. Over time, however, the negative effects diminish. In the long run, FDI has a positive impact on DI, where a 1% increase in FDI inflows results in more than a 1% increase in domestic investment. Conversely, GDP growth has a significant and negative effect on DI in the long run, while the short-run impact is positive and significant.

The results also indicate that both DI and GDP growth are factors influencing FDI inflows, but the effects are weak and significant only in the long run.

We strongly believe that one of the main reasons for the crowding-out effect in the short run is the lack of absorptive capacity among domestic firms and weak financial sector development. As highlighted in previous chapters, R&D and innovation are among the main factors that determine absorptive capacity (Cohen & Levinthal, 1990; Xiaolan Fu, 2008; Nguyen et al., 2009; Murovec & Prodan, 2009). According to the IV Business Registration (IV-RE), of 3,067 companies with organized accounts in Cape Verde, only 201 reported engaging in innovation activities (product, process,

organizational, or marketing) during 2013–2014. This confirms the limited absorptive capacity of domestic firms and highlights the need for further research in this field.

In conclusion, the effects of FDI on DI in Cape Verde are mixed: FDI crowds out DI in the short run but crowds it in over the long run. Additionally, DI plays a role in attracting FDI inflows.

5.1 Policy Implications

Firstly, the government should adopt policies to strengthen the capacity of domestic investment and enhance absorptive capacity, as these are key channels through which DI can benefit from FDI spillovers. Improving human capital, infrastructure, institutions, and technology is essential to maximizing the benefits of FDI.

The government should also encourage foreign investors to invest in industrial sectors where DI lacks technological capacity, particularly in the fisheries sector. Through interactions with multinational corporations (MNCs), domestic firms could benefit from spillover effects and contribute to a more dynamic market.

Finally, policies that improve domestic firms' access to financing—such as bank loans or alternative sources of credit—are necessary to enable firms to expand and better absorb FDI spillovers.

5.2 Limitations and Suggestions for Further Research

One of the main limitations of this study is the relatively small sample size, as FDI data is only available from 1986 to 2015. With a larger dataset, the findings could provide even more robust insights. Another limitation is the scarcity of prior research on this topic in Cape Verde.

For future studies, we strongly recommend analyzing the impact of FDI inflows at the sectoral level to identify which sectors attract the most investment and how they benefit the economy. This would provide more detailed guidance for policymakers to design targeted FDI strategies.

Additionally, further research should examine the absorptive capacity of domestic firms to assess whether DI truly benefits from FDI. Survey-based studies with

domestic companies could provide valuable insights into how firms interact with foreign investors and whether knowledge spillovers occur.

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Appendix 1- Plot of Series under Studies

